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**EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TYPES AND APPLICATION RATES OF
SUPERPHOSPHATE ON SEED GERMINATION AND SEEDLING
DENSITY OF THE “ANDIJAN-37” COTTON VARIETY**

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Annotation. The article aims to determine the effects of various phosphorus fertilizers produced at the “Indorama” plant under the “Oltin” brand on seed germination and seedling density of the Andijan-37 cotton variety.

Keywords: "Golden" brand, ASSP, Ammophos, growth dynamics, density standing, soil sample, growth period, productive branches.

Introduction.

Relevance and necessity of production-oriented research.

At present, achieving high and quality yields in agriculture largely depends on the timely and rate-based implementation of various agrotechnical measures, particularly proper fertilization of cotton. Applying nutrients at recommended rates and appropriate times accelerates boll formation and opening, increases cotton yield, and enables harvesting within a shorter period.

Cotton is cultivated in 89 countries worldwide, with total fiber production amounting to 16.63 million tons. The largest cotton-growing areas are located in Asia, covering 17.02 million hectares. In North and Central America, industrial cotton plantations occupy 4.38 million hectares, including 4.06 million hectares in the United States. Africa ranks third in cotton cultivation, with an area of 4.2 million hectares.

Obtaining high yields from cotton fields requires the correct determination of seedling density per hectare and timely fertilization at prescribed rates, which are among the most important agrotechnical practices. Uzbekistan is one of the world's major cotton-producing countries and is characterized by sharply continental soil and climatic conditions. Therefore, depending on regional soil and climate characteristics, it is necessary to maintain optimal seedling density and apply fertilizers at appropriate times and rates, taking into account the morpho-biological characteristics of cotton varieties. From this perspective, developing pinching (topping) schedules based on seedling density and varietal morpho-biological traits is of great importance.

Each newly developed cotton variety is studied with consideration of its morphological characteristics in relation to sowing dates, seedling density, irrigation regimes, and fertilizer application timing and rates. As a result, effective pinching periods and various methods of treatment with chemical retardants have been developed by taking these agrotechnical measures into account. However, scientific research aimed at determining optimal pinching timing and methods depending on seedling density for newly developed cotton varieties remains insufficient.

In the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the priority tasks is defined as “the introduction of intensive methods in agricultural production, especially modern agrotechnologies that save water and other resources.” Therefore, in order to ensure intensive land use, conducting scientific research on cotton cultivation practices—including the use of new fertilizers, optimal seedling density, and pinching methods and timing—is considered highly relevant.

Purpose of the research. The aim of this study is to determine the effects of various mineral fertilizers produced at the “Indorama” plant under the “Oltin” brand

on the growth, development, yield, and fiber quality of cotton in cooperation with the Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies.

Experimental System

№	Variates	Norm P205	Fon kg/ga
1	OLTIN ASSP: Application based on Soil test report recommendation	776кг/га	N-250 K-60
2	NOVOIY AZOT ASSP: Application based on Soil test report recommendation	776кг/га	N-250 K-60
3	FERGANA AZOT ASSP: Application based on Soil test report recommendation.	776кг/га	N-250 K-60
4	Control plot: No P205 would be given.	-	N-250 K-60

The Influence of Phosphorus Fertilizer Types and Rates on the Seedling Emergence and Stand Density of the “Andijan-37” Cotton Variety

It is known that all new cotton varieties require specific agrotechnical measures under different soil-climatic conditions. In particular, although the “Andijan-37” cotton variety was developed for the climatic conditions of the Fergana Valley, it necessitates the development of its own agrotechnical practices. For this reason, it is considered an important task to develop optimal sowing methods and mineral fertilizer rates for the light sierozem (gray) soils of the Andijan region, specifically regarding their effect on seedling emergence and plant stand density requirements.

According to scientific sources, a certain level of soil moisture and temperature is necessary for seedling emergence. Scientific literature indicates that in autumn-plowed fields, an additional temperature of 1.5–2.0°C is generated compared to flat fields. Therefore, regardless of the sowing method, seeds provided with the moisture and temperature available on the ridges germinate quickly and healthily. Especially under natural soil moisture conditions, pre-sprouted cotton seeds produce a uniform and full stand.

In the first experiment, studying the effect of different superphosphate brands on cotton germination and stand density, the growth dynamics were observed over 4 periods. At the beginning of the growing season, the first variant using "Oltin SSP" resulted in 119.0 thousand plants/ha. By the end of the season, this indicator decreased by 2.1% compared to the beginning, amounting to 116.7 thousand plants/ha. This figure was 11.5 thousand plants/ha higher than the second variant using Navoi SSP, 9.1 thousand plants/ha higher than the third variant using Fergana SSP, and 14.6 thousand plants/ha higher than the control. Data on cotton stand density and growth rate from the first experiment are presented in Table 3.1.1 below.

In the second experiment, studying the effect of applying "Oltin SSP" and Ammophos fertilizers in different ratios on the stand density of the Andijan-35 variety, at the beginning of the growing season the first variant using 100% Oltin SSP (776 kg/ha) relative to the soil test resulted in 114.1 thousand plants/ha. Before harvesting, this indicator decreased by 2.5% compared to the beginning of the season, amounting to 111.3 thousand plants/ha at the end of the period. It was observed that this indicator was 2.3 thousand plants/ha lower in the second (Oltin SSP 120% - 932 kg/ha) and third (Oltin SSP 80% - 621 kg/ha) variants, where it was 119 thousand plants at the beginning and 116.7 thousand plants at the end of the growing season, respectively.

Var.№	Growth Dynamics %				Stand density at the beginning of the growing season	Stand density at the end of the growing season
	20.04	23.04	26.04	29.04		
OLTIN ASSP	20,2	47,7	68,0	89,9	119,0	116,7
NOVOI Y AZOT ASSP	18,9	45,6	64,5	82,5	108,0	105,2
FERGANA AZOT ASSP	19,5	46,2	65,3	83,8	110,1	107,6
Control	18,4	44,5	63,6	81,8	106,1	102,1

In the second experiment, which studied the effect of applying "Oltin SSP" and Ammophos fertilizers in different ratios on the stand density and degree of overwintering of winter wheat, the stand density at the beginning of the growing season in the first variant—where 100% Oltin SSP (776 kg/ha) relative to the soil test was applied—amounted to 114.1 thousand plants/ha. Before harvesting, this indicator decreased by 2.5% compared to the beginning of the season, and by the end of the growing season it amounted to 111.3 thousand plants/ha. It was observed that this indicator was 5.5 thousand plants/ha lower in the second variant (Oltin SSP 120% - 932 kg/ha) and 7.0 thousand plants/ha higher in the third variant (Oltin SSP

80% - 621 kg/ha) compared to the end of the growing season, respectively.

In the fourth variant, where 100% Ammophos (287 kg/ha) fertilizer was applied, the stand density at the beginning of the growing season was 112.2 thousand plants/ha. By the end of the vegetation period, it decreased by 2.5% compared to the beginning of the season, and by the end of the growing season this indicator amounted to 108.1 thousand plants/ha. It was observed that this indicator was 3.5 thousand plants/ha lower in the fifth variant (Ammophos 120% - 344 kg/ha) and 4.2 thousand plants/ha higher in the sixth variant (Ammophos 80% - 230 kg/ha) compared to the end of the growing season, respectively.

In the second experiment, where "Oltin SSP" and Ammophos fertilizers were tested at different application rates, the best results were obtained in the second variant using Oltin SSP 120% (930 kg/ha). Specifically, the average plant height measured over three periods was as follows: 17.3 cm on June 1, 56.6 cm on July 1, and 110.4 cm on August 1. These figures were 0.8 cm higher on June 1, 2.8 cm higher on July 1, and 3.2 cm higher on August 1 compared to the fifth variant where the corresponding rate of Ammophos was applied.

Var	1 june		1 july		1 august			1 september	
	Main Stem Height, cm	Number of True Leaves, units	Main Stem Height, cm	Number of Productive Branches, units	Main Stem Height, cm	Number of field Components, units	Number of Capsules, units	Number of Capsules, units	Number of harvested units

					units			units			s	
Oltin assp	1 6,6	5 ,9	5 0,6	5 ,1	5 ,2	07,3	1 2,9	1 6,8	1 ,4	6 4,2	9 ,7	
No voiy azot assp	1 6,3	5 ,5	5 4,6	4 ,9	4 ,5	01,4	1 2,1	1 4,4	1 ,1	5 ,8	7 ,7	
Fer gana azot assp	1 6,5	5 ,5	5 9,1	5 ,0	5 ,1	7,0	1 2,8	1 5,7	1 ,6	5 0,2	8 ,0	
Con trol	1 3,2	3 ,7	3 3,5	4 ,1	4 ,8	7,0	1 0,5	1 0,8	1 ,7	3 ,0	4 ,8	

Regarding the indicators for the **number of true leaves**, it was also observed that in the second variant where **Oltin SSP 120% (930 kg/ha)** was applied, **5.9 leaves per plant** were produced during the initial observation period. This was **0.3 leaves more** than the fifth variant where Ammophos was applied at a 120% rate.

Concerning the **number of productive branches (fruiting branches)**, the highest indicator was also obtained in the second variant where **Oltin SSP 120% (930 kg/ha)** was applied. It amounted to **5.3 branches** in the observation period of **July 1** and **13.7 branches** in the observation period of **August 1**.

In conclusion, as evident from the data in the tables above, at this developmental stage, providing the cotton crop with adequate phosphorus mineral fertilizers resulted in **reduced seedling mortality and losses** observed at the beginning of the vegetation period. In particular, the treatments using "**Oltin**"

brand ammoniated single superphosphate fertilizer from the *Indorama* plant and complex **NPK fertilizers** demonstrated higher effectiveness.

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